

Observability Solutions

December 2024

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Agenda

- Current Architecture and Challenges
- Overview of Business Requirements
- Grafana Labs Observability Solutions

Current Architecture and Challenges

- Customer is using observability tools from different vendors such as Splunk, New Relic and InfluxDB.
- It makes the integration and correlation of data between different vendors difficult.
- Using multiple vendors can result in higher cost.
- Limited support and higher operational overhead since customer needs to deal with different support teams.
- Instrumentation and collecting telemetry data for infrastructure and applications are done with vendor-specific SDK and agents that it leads to vendor lock-in.

Current Architecture and Challenges

- Customer environments are distributed across on-prem and various public cloud providers
- InfluxDB has faced scalability challenges in the past
- Customer wants to see how the GrafanaLabs Observability Stack can help them to resolve their business challenges

Business Requirements

- Enhance the scalability of the observability stack
- Reduce MTTI(mean time to identify) by having more visibility and correlation between telemetry data
- Auto instrumentation of the applications
- Enabling vendor-neutral collection of telemetry data
- Migrating to an unified observability stack without downtime and impact
- Full control over the telemetry data(logs, metrics, and traces)

GrafanaLabs Observability Solutions

- Using Grafana Alloy as an open source OpenTelemetry collector for collecting telemetry data from different data sources and agents
- Grafana Alloy is installed and used in parallel with the existing third party agents and start scraping logs, metrics and traces
- Grafana Beyla can be used as an option for auto instrumentation of the applications with no code change (can be used for the new application deployments that are not instrumented by SDK or any agent)

GrafanaLabs Observability Solutions

- Deployment of backends Loki(for logs), Tempo(for traces) and Mimir(for metrics) and Grafana for visualization (Grafana Enterprise)
- Phased migration to Grafana Labs observability stack and backends to prevent any downtime and impact

About OpenTelemetry

- OpenTelemetry is a framework for instrumenting, collecting and sending telemetry data to the backends.
- It defines a pipeline that data follows in the collector from receiver, to processing, and finally to export.

OpenTelemetry Collector

- Avoid vendor lock-in, It lets you switch backend providers
- Sending same data to multiple backends
- Agents and SDK's are not vendor specific and you can export the data to any supported backend exporters even if they don't support OTLP (cross protocol support, act as translation layer). As an example InfluxDB doesn't support OTLP.
- Unified telemetry, collection of all metrics, logs and traces under one single framework/collector
- Makes it easier for correlation of data and helps for MTTI
- Auto-instrumentation (agent based or eBPF based)

Grafana Alloy

- Grafana Alloy is an open source OpenTelemetry collector

Alloy config to collect metrics from Kubernetes Pods in the default Namespace:

```
discovery.kubernetes "pods" {
  role = "pod"

  namespaces {
    own_namespace = false

    names = ["default"]
  }

  selectors {
    role = "pod"
    label = "scrape"
  }
}

prometheus.scrape "pods" {
  targets      = discovery.kubernetes.pods.targets
  forward_to = [prometheus.remote_write.default.receiver]
}

prometheus.remote_write "default" {
  endpoint {
    url = "http://localhost:9090/api/prom/push"
  }
}
```

Instrumentation

- To make a system observable, it must be instrumented. The instrumented data must then be sent to an observability backend.
- Can be done manually or automatically
- Manually is done by using SDKs. To align with unified telemetry, use the SDKs provided by OpenTelemetry framework.
- Automatically can be done in two ways, agent based or ebpf based.
- Opentelemetry Operator provides an agent based instrumentation using K8s CRDs.

OpenTelemetry Auto-Instrumentation

```
apiVersion: opentelemetry.io/v1alpha1
kind: Instrumentation
metadata:
  name: auto-instrumentation
spec:
  exporter:
    endpoint: http://appdynamics-otel-collector-service.appdynamics.svc.cluster.local:4317
  propagators:
  - tracecontext
  - baggage
  env:
  - name: OTEL_EXPORTER_OTLP_INSECURE
    value: "true"
  - name: OTEL_LOG_LEVEL
    value: "debug"
  - name: OTEL_TRACES_EXPORTER
    value: "otlp,logging"
  java:
    image: ghcr.io/open-telemetry/opentelemetry-operator/autoinstrumentation-java:latest
    env:
    - name: OTEL_EXPORTER_OTLP_ENDPOINT
      value: "http://appdynamics-otel-collector-service.appdynamics.svc.cluster.local:4317"
    - name: OTEL_JAVAAGENT_DEBUG
      value: "true"
  nodejs:
    image: ghcr.io/open-telemetry/opentelemetry-operator/autoinstrumentation-nodejs:latest
    env:
    - name: OTEL_EXPORTER_OTLP_ENDPOINT
      value: "http://appdynamics-otel-collector-service.appdynamics.svc.cluster.local:4317"
  python:
    image: ghcr.io/open-telemetry/opentelemetry-operator/autoinstrumentation-python:0.28b1
    env:
    - name: OTEL_EXPORTER_OTLP_TRACES_ENDPOINT
      value: "http://appdynamics-otel-collector-service.appdynamics.svc.cluster.local:4318/v1/traces"
    - name: OTEL_TRACES_EXPORTER
      value: otlp_proto_http
    - name: OTEL_PYTHON_LOG_LEVEL
      value: "debug"
  dotnet:
    env:
    - name: OTEL_EXPORTER_OTLP_ENDPOINT
      value: http://appdynamics-otel-collector-service.appdynamics.svc.cluster.local:4318
```

Auto Instrumentation with Grafana Beyla

- Grafana Beyla is an eBPF-based application auto-instrumentation tool
- It doesn't need any application code change, it intercepts the system calls and by detecting the runtime can instrument the application.
- Beyla then pushes the captured traces and metrics to the Alloy over OTLP protocol.

Architectural Comparison between GrafanaLabs and InfluxDB for Backend

- **Grafana Labs (Loki, Mimir, Tempo):**
 - Separation of Concerns:
 - Loki: Optimized for storing and querying logs.
 - Mimir: Specialized for metrics with scalability and high-performance aggregation.
 - Tempo: Designed for traces, focusing on high-throughput ingestion and query efficiency.
 - Each backend can scale independently based on the load.
 - Each backend is tailored for a specific type of telemetry data, allowing independent scaling, storage optimization, and query efficiency.

- **InfluxDB:**

- Unified Backend:

- Stores all types of telemetry data (metrics, logs, traces) in a single database.
 - Efficient for time-series data, but treating logs and traces as time-series can introduce challenges in query performance and storage optimization.
 - All telemetry data share the same storage and compute resources, which can become a bottleneck at high scale.

Proposed Architecture

Thank you

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